

PROCESSING POLYETHYLENE/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES FROM BENTONITE PREPARED FROM PERSIAN CLAY

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Abstract:

Na- type Bentonite that supplied from Kheirbad mine benefitted before treating with two types of quaternary ammonium salts. After the treatment, the powder was characterized by X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy. Nanocomposites containing polyethylene (PE) and oligomerically modified clay (OMC) were obtained via direct melt intercalation. The mechanical properties and characteristic of prepared nanocomposite investigated and compared with nanocomposite that produced from Cloisite 15A in the same condition. As the gallery distance in Kheirabad modified nanoclay is more than Cloisite15A, its dispersion is better while increasing Young's modulus but, tensile strength and relative elongation decreases.

Introduction:

In recent years Polymer-clay nanocomposites have been attracting academic and industrial interest because of the anticipated considerable improvement in properties, such as stiffness, gas barrier, flammability, etc. when the aluminosilicate platelets of clay like montmorillonite are well exfoliated into polymer. The first systematic work on a polymer/clay system was conducted involving the nylon 6/montmorillonite system by Toyota Inc. [1, 2]. Recent studies have shown that organically modified clay may efficiently exfoliated in polar polymer like polyamides using appropriate techniques and conditions [2-6]. For the more commonly used polyolefins like polyethylene or polypropylene, synthesis of well-exfoliated nanocomposite appears to be more difficult. The hydrophobic nature of polyolefins decreases interaction's affinity with aluminosilicate surface of the clay.

Two common approaches to produce nanocomposite involves in situ polymerization and melt compounding. The latter is more immediately useful from an industrial point of view. The most purposed strategy to achieve exfoliated structure is to add a small amount of maleic anhydride grafted polyolefin that is miscible with the base polyolefin [7-9]. It is believed that the polar character of the anhydride causes affinity for the clay materials such that the maleated polyolefin can serve as a 'compatibilizer' between the matrix and filler [10-21]. But adding this compatibilizer has undesirable effects on properties of nanocomposite[8, 17].

In this paper a sample of organoclay was made by purifying bentonite and modifying it by quaternary ammonium salt and the produced composite properties was compared with the one prepared from commercial grade.

Experimental:

The pristine clay used was Na-Montmorillonite provided from Kheirabad mine in Kerman, Iran. Milled bentonite by laboratory ball mill up to 100 mesh, stirred with distilled water for 2 hours and then pure Montmorillonite separated by sedimentation. To attain oligomerically modified clay of Kheirabad (OMCK), the purified Na-MMT was mixed in distilled water with stirring to form a uniformly dispersed suspension. The suspension was stirred for 20 min after all the clay has been added. And then the dimethyl dioctadecyl ammonium chloride equivalent to 1.2 CEC of Na-MMT was added into the dispersion. The mixture was stirred for 20 min. After 24 h, the mixture of montmorillonite and the salt was washed with distilled water for several times to remove excess

Table 1

Materials that used in this study

Material	Commercial name	Description	Supplier
Organoclay Na-Montmorillonite	Closite 15A	CEC=125, $d_{100}=31.5\text{\AA}$ CEC=78, swelling index=18	Southern Clay Products, Inc. Kheirabad mine
High density polyethylene	usex6100	Density=0.952, Melt index: 0.052 g/10min	Skyenergy

salts, dried at 60 °C for 48 h, and finally, passed in a sieve 200 meshes.

Closite 15A was supplied by the Southern Clay Products that modified by dimethyl dehydrogenated Tallow quaternary ammonium. Pt 100 class HDPE delivered from Skyenergy (usex6100). More details about the materials used are given in Table 1.

All composites prepared by melt compounding in Brabender Plasticorder static mixer of 50ml capacity, preheated to 170°C. The rotor speed mentioned at 80rpm. The overall blending time was 10 min. The mixed samples were transferred to a mold and preheated at 170°C for 3min, then pressed at 14MPa, and successively cooled to room temperature while maintaining the pressure to obtain the composite sheets for further measurements. Table 2 gives the composition of the nanocomposites.

Table 2

Composition of polyethylene clay nanocomposites

Sample	OMCK	Closite 15A
PE	-	-
C11	-	1
C13	-	3
C15	-	5
C110	-	10
Ke1	1	-
Ke3	3	-
Ke5	5	-
Ke10	10	-

The structure of PE/clay composites was characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) test. XRD patterns between angles 1.3° and 10° were obtained with an X'Pert Philips diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ filtered radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) at 50 kV, 40 mA.

Tensile tests were conducted on an Instron universal material test machine. Tensile strength was determined at a crosshead speed of 100mm/min.

Results and Discussions:

The effect of organic modifier on the morphology of clay is shown in the Fig. 1 which is the x-ray diffraction patterns of the samples.

Fig. 1 XRD patterns of unmodified and modified montmorillonite clay (MMT)

It can be observed that the unmodified clay (MMT) has a peak corresponding to an interlayer spacing $d_{001} = 12.5\text{\AA}$. This interlayer spacing for the treated sample with quaternary ammonium salt, obtained from the corresponding XRD pattern, is 38.50\AA . Another two peaks were observed, ascribed to the interlayer spacing $d_{002} = 19.45\text{\AA}$, in which occurred the intercalation of the salt between the layers of organoclay and interlayer spacing of 12.5\AA is probably due to an incomplete ion exchange, with some residual Na-MMT remaining in the material. The interlayer distance is determined by the diffraction peak in the X-ray method, using the Bragg equation. The results indicated that the quaternary ammonium salt was intercalated between two basal planes of MMT, leading to a considerable expansion of the interlayer spacing. As a matter of fact, the d_{001} spacing had risen upon the treatment with the quaternary ammonium salt.

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of nanocomposite contain 1% OMC

Fig. 3 XRD patterns of nanocomposite contain 5% OMC

Fig. 4 XRD patterns of nanocomposite contain 3% OMC

Fig. 5 XRD patterns of nanocomposite contain 10% OMC

The XRD patterns of PE nanocomposites are shown in Figs. 2-5 while the corresponding compositions are reported in Table 2.

For PE nanocomposites, 1 and 3% organoclay gives peaks with low intensity while 5 and 10% organoclay shows much higher intensity, and the 001 reflection is slightly shifted to a lower 2θ value. By Adding 3% OMCK the clay's peaks vanishes which means full exfoliation of the clay in the matrix. In other compositions OMCK show larger gallery distance than Cloisite15A that signify better intercalated structure.

The mechanical properties of the nanocomposites have been measured and compared to those of

polyethylene in Table 3. The tensile strength and its elongation are decreased by increasing the percent of organoclay and its effect is much higher for composites containing more than 5% organoclay. The yield strength and its elongation are not change significantly and, Young's modulus for these nanocomposites increases monotonically by increasing nanoclay. In spite of the higher Young's modulus for 10% nanoclay, it is not recommended due to catastrophic effect on tensile strength.

Conclusions:

Modified clay was prepared from bentonite of Kheirabad mine and its properties were evaluated

Table 3 mechanical properties of nanocomposites

	Tensile Strength MPa	Elongation at Tensile Strength %	Yield Strength MPa	Elongation at yield Strength %	Young's modulus MPa
PE	32.43	1037.07	19.85	17.80	200.42
Cl1	31.43	980.06	20.90	16.74	204.79
Cl3	28.37	884.22	20.79	17.41	283.48
Cl5	29.10	904.48	20.91	16.75	313.91
Cl10	21.12	15.07	21.12	17.14	280.48
Ke1	27.51	875.13	20.78	16.68	273.00
Ke3	30.00	948.15	20.87	16.35	297.19
Ke5	25.32	815.26	20.41	16.42	275.86
Ke10	20.89	14.23	20.89	16.34	303.17

using XRD and compared with Cloisite15A. Polyethylene nanocomposites were successfully prepared in a Brabender Plasticorder static mixer with these nanoclays and the resultant XRD patterns and mechanical properties were compared. The results show that by addition of either Cloisite15A or OMCK between 3-5% in polyethylene give the best results, while the OMCK nanocomposite is slightly better than Cloisite15A nanocomposites.

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